

The generalized setup of comprehensive thermodynamic theory of stability of irreversible processes (CTTSIP) and a few illustrative applications[‡]¶

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A generalized setup of the recently developed comprehensive thermodynamic theory of stability of irreversible processes (CTTSIP) has been described. In the first place, it involves expressing thermodynamic Lyapunov function, L_s (defined in the perturbation space) and the entropy source strength, σ_s , corresponding to the perturbed trajectory as the Taylor expansion about their values on the real (unperturbed) trajectory whose thermodynamic stability is under investigation. In this way all quantities are obtained that are tenable within the thermodynamic perturbation space and hence one is led to the autonomous mathematical description. Yet another advantage is that in a single setup there is now available an apparatus to determine thermodynamic stability against uni- and bilateral perturbations and correspondingly first and higher order stability considerations are also dealt with as the case may be. Of course, all cases are handled with the fabric of celebrated Lyapunov's second (direct) method of stability of motion. A few representative examples have been described to illustrate how this generalized setup of CTTSIP works. The conclusions about the stability, asymptotic stability, stability against the constantly acting small disturbances and instability are drawn using Lyapunov and Malkin theorems.

A powerful apparatus for investigation of stability of dynamic systems is that of Lyapunov¹⁻⁵. We recall that the primary ingredient of any stability enquiry is to effect a sufficiently small perturbation and then determine the evolution of the system under the constraints of the corresponding unperturbed trajectory¹. This is what indeed is followed in Lyapunov's two methods of stability of motion. In his first method one is required to solve the differential equations of the perturbed motion and hence in it we handle the cases on an individual basis. Whereas, his second (also termed as direct) method has a generality element akin to thermodynamics. Herein one identifies a sign definite function dependent on the coordinates of perturbed motion and then its total time derivative is determined. Thus one is not required to solve the differential equations of motion.

On the other hand, thermodynamic stability considerations that are available in literature have so far exploited the impossibilities established by the second law of thermodynamics which determines the unnatural direction of a transition of a system⁶⁻¹⁵. Thus these theories use the concept of virtual displacement from the given state of the system, which in turn make them more geometric in nature

rather than that based on a real (sufficiently small) perturbation. They tend to create an impression that one is considering only those perturbations originating from the natural fluctuations. However, as the natural fluctuation is a probabilistic phenomenon and as such is not covered by the time scales dictated by the laws of thermodynamics^{9,16-18}, how far these existing theories fall within the thermodynamic fold remains an open query.

The present author has recently developed a new thermodynamic theory for investigating stability of real processes¹⁶⁻¹⁸. In this theory the thermodynamic Lyapunov function has been identified as the excess entropy source strength with respect to unperturbed trajectory and then its total time rate is determined in the perturbation space as described in Lyapunov's second method. This theory has been termed as comprehensive thermodynamic theory of stability of irreversible processes (CTTSIP). Within the framework of this theory we have already investigated the stability of (i) equilibrium and nonequilibrium stationary states (NSS)¹⁸, (ii) the rigid body heat conduction¹⁶, (iii) the stress relaxational processes in viscoelastic fluids^{19,20} and (iv) a few elementary chemical reactions proceeding at

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finite rates^{21,22}. These investigations have established a procedure for coping with the real perturbations that are much bigger than those envisaged on account of natural fluctuations. However, it has been realized that as the perturbations involved in the stability analysis is sufficiently small (but larger than that in natural fluctuations) it would be much better to make CTTSIP a much more compact apparatus similar to Gibbs-Duhem stability theory^{6,7,11,13,15}. The following sections describe in sequel the generalized setup of CTTSIP and its applications in determining the stability of general equilibrium states, chemical equilibrium against the perturbations in mole numbers and temperature and rigid body heat conduction, and finally concluding remarks follow.

The generalized setup of CTTSIP

Let $x_i^0(t)$ be the thermodynamic coordinates of the process on the unperturbed trajectory and $x_i(t)$ that on the perturbed one. The perturbation coordinates then get defined as,

$$\alpha_i(t) = (x_i(t) - x_i^0(t)) \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

and hence the equation of unperturbed trajectory is obtained as,

$$\alpha_i^0(t) \equiv 0 \quad (2)$$

Thus $\alpha_i(t)$'s determine the thermodynamic perturbation space. The constitutive equations of motion within the perturbation space in general are described as,

$$\frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} = f_i(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, t) \quad (3)$$

In CTTSIP¹⁶⁻²² the thermodynamic Lyapunov function, L_s , is defined as,

$$L_s(t) = (\sigma_s(t) - \sigma_s^0(t)) \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_s(t)$ and $\sigma_s^0(t)$ are the respective entropy source strengths. Hence, L_s is the excess rate of entropy production per unit volume. Obviously, we have,

$$L_s = L_s(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, t) > 0$$

or

$$L_s = L_s(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, t) < 0 \quad (5)$$

and hence on the unperturbed trajectory we have,

$$L_s^0 = L_s(0, 0, 0, \dots, t) \equiv 0 \quad (6)$$

As we need to work within the thermodynamic perturbation space let us expand $\sigma_s(t)$ in terms of $\alpha_i(t)$'s that gives,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_s - \sigma_s^0 &= \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \alpha_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j + \\ &\frac{1}{6} \sum_{i,j,k} \left(\frac{\partial^3 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j \partial \alpha_k} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \alpha_k + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Notice that, for the sake of brevity the time dependence of quantities has not been shown. The thermodynamic Lyapunov function, L_s , is then given as (cf. eq. (7)),

$$\begin{aligned} L_s &= \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \alpha_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j + \\ &\frac{1}{6} \sum_{i,j,k} \left(\frac{\partial^3 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j \partial \alpha_k} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \alpha_k + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Thus, even the bilateral perturbations can also be treated by this formalism.

Alternatively, L_s can be expanded directly in terms of α_i 's as,

$$\begin{aligned} L_s &= \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \alpha_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j + \\ &\frac{1}{6} \sum_{i,j,k} \left(\frac{\partial^3 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j \partial \alpha_k} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \alpha_k + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

(i) However, if $(\partial \sigma_s / \partial \alpha_i)^0 \neq 0$ and hence $(\partial L_s / \partial \alpha_i)^0 \neq 0$, and as per the requirement of Lyapunov's theory of stability of motion¹⁻⁵ α_i 's need to be sufficiently small the higher order terms in the expansion of $\sigma_s(t)$ and $L_s(t)$ can be ignored and hence the expressions for them get restricted to,

$$\sigma_s - \sigma_s^0 \approx \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \alpha_i \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_s &= (\sigma_s - \sigma_s^0) \approx \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \alpha_i \\ &= \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \alpha_i \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In eq. (11) each $(\partial L_s / \partial \alpha_i)^0$ is either positive or negative.

The preceding assertion gets elaborated on differentiating eq. (11) as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_j} &= \left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 = \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_j} \left(\sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \alpha_i \right) \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The total time derivative of L_s then reads as,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = \frac{\partial L_s}{\partial t} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right) \frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} \quad (13)$$

which transforms to,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = \sum_i \alpha_i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 + \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^0 \frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} \quad (14)$$

The conclusions about the stability of a process are then drawn on establishing the sign of dL_s/dt and whether the magnitude of each $(\partial L_s/\partial \alpha_i)_t$ is finite or not as per Malkin's theorem^{4,5}.

(ii) On the other hand, if $(\partial \sigma_s/\partial \alpha_i)^0 = 0$ and hence $(\partial L_s/\partial \alpha_i)^0 = 0$ and as stated above in view of the requirement of Lyapunov's theory of stability of motion¹⁻⁵ α_i 's need to be sufficiently small the third and higher order terms in the expansion of $\sigma_s(t)$ and $L_s(t)$ can be ignored and hence the expressions for them get reduced to,

$$\sigma_s - \sigma_s^0 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_s - L_s^0 &= (\sigma_s - \sigma_s^0) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The differentiation of eq. (16) successively with respect to α_k and α_l produces the following two expressions, namely :

$$\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_k} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial^2 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_k} \right)^0 \alpha_i$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_k} \left(\sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \alpha_i \alpha_j \right) \\ &= \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_k} \right)^0 \alpha_i \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_k} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_k} \right)^0 = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_k} \right)^0 \geq 0 \quad (18)$$

The total time rate of L_s then reads as,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_s}{dt} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \alpha_i \alpha_j \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \\ &+ \sum_j \left(\sum_i \alpha_i \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \right) \frac{d\alpha_j}{dt} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where we have used the following expression for the local time derivative of L_s , namely :

$$\left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial t} \right)_\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \alpha_i \alpha_j \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^0 \quad (20)$$

Thermodynamic stability is then determined by finding out the sign of dL_s/dt on the lines of Lyapunov's direct method of stability of motion¹⁻⁵ that in nutshell reads as — the identified sign definite Lyapunov function of coordinates of the motion under investigation and its total time derivative must have opposite signs to guarantee its Lyapunov stability.

However, the same procedure gets extended if upto $(n-1)$ -th derivatives of σ_s happen to vanish at the origin. In this event one needs to obtain and use the n -th derivative of σ_s at the origin.

Representative applications

Now for the sake of demonstration we consider in sequel some of the elementary examples and determine their stability using the above described setup of CTTSIP. The first one is that of general equilibrium state followed by the case of a single chemical reaction at equilibrium. In the next section the case of rigid body heat conduction has been described.

Thermodynamic stability of equilibrium states. The generalized treatment :

The description of stability of equilibrium states within the above described framework follows as under.

(i) The simple case is when the first differential of L_s at equilibrium is non-zero. For an equilibrium state by definition we have $\sigma_s^e = 0$ and hence L_s reads as,

$$L_s = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e \alpha_i = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e \alpha_i > 0 \quad (21)$$

In arriving at eq. (21) we have used the fact that on perturbation a neighbouring nonequilibrium state is attained and hence there we have,

$$\alpha_i > 0, \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e > 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \alpha_i < 0, \left(\frac{\partial \delta_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e < 0 \quad (22)$$

The superscript e denotes an equilibrium state. As an equilibrium state is time invariant we also have by definition,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e = 0 \quad (23)$$

and hence eq. (14) in the present case reads as,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e \frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} \quad (24)$$

However, it is an observed fact that each $d|\alpha_i|/dt < 0$ (that is $d\alpha_i/dt > 0$ for $\alpha_i < 0$ and $d\alpha_i/dt < 0$ for $\alpha_i > 0$) that vanishes only at the origin and as each gradient of L_s in the perturbation space is positive and finite, that is,

$$\left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e = \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e \quad \text{and finite} \quad (25)$$

and hence in view of eqs. (22) and (24) we have,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i} \right)^e \frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (26)$$

where β is a strictly positive number that vanishes only at the origin. Thus eq. (26) establishes that equilibrium states are asymptotically stable. Moreover, in view of eq. (25) and Malkin's theorem⁴ equilibrium states are obtained as stable under the constantly acting small disturbances.

(ii) However, when the first differential of L_s at equilib-

rium vanishes but its second differential at equilibrium happens to be finite we need to tackle such cases accordingly. In this case the thermodynamic stability of an equilibrium state gets the following description. As already stated above, for an equilibrium state by definition we have $\sigma_s^e = 0$ and hence L_s reads as,

$$\begin{aligned} L_s &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^e \alpha_i \alpha_j \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^e \alpha_i \alpha_j > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Notice that in this case from eq. (27) we do have,

$$\alpha_j > 0, \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^e \alpha_i > 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \alpha_j < 0, \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^e \alpha_i < 0 \quad (28)$$

The total time derivative of L_s then reads as,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = \sum_{i,j} \alpha_i \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^e \frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (29)$$

The result of eq. (29) follows in view of eq. (28) and from the fact that each $d|\alpha_j|/dt < 0$. Further, we have,

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 L_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^e = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha_i \partial \alpha_j} \right)^e \quad \text{and finite} \quad (30)$$

Thus eq. (29) establishes that equilibrium states are asymptotically stable. Moreover, as per Malkin's theorem⁴ and eq. (30) equilibrium states are obtained as stable under the constantly acting small disturbances. Of course, these conclusions are not new but the method of arriving them is new and lucid because of the present CTTSIP setup.

Indeed, these are the same conclusions, which we have earlier obtained¹⁶.

The case of chemical equilibrium :

Consider a chemically reactive spatially uniform system at equilibrium. Further, assume that the perturbations are such that no spatial non-uniformity gets generated.

Perturbation of extent of advancement of reaction :

In this case on perturbation the chemical reaction starts proceeding at a finite rate and hence the entropy production reads as^{6,7,10,11,13,15},

$$\sigma_s = \frac{\mathcal{A} d\xi}{T dt} > 0 \quad (31)$$

Now define α as,

$$\alpha \equiv (\xi - \xi^e) \quad (32)$$

As at equilibrium we have $d\xi^e/dt = 0$, after perturbation a finite rate of reaction gets generated that determines the positive direction of the process, that is $d\xi/dt > 0$ and hence we have $\xi < \xi^e$. Thus in the present case we have,

$$\frac{d(\xi - \xi^e)}{dt} > 0 \quad (33)$$

But in view of $\xi < \xi^e$ we have $-\delta\xi = \xi - \xi^e = -\alpha$ hence from eq. (33) we have,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} < 0 \quad (34)$$

and therefore eq. (31) reads as,

$$\sigma_s = \frac{\mathcal{A} d\alpha}{T dt} > 0 \quad (35)$$

From eq. (35) we obtain,

$$\left(\frac{\partial\sigma_s}{\partial\alpha}\right) = -\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\right)\right)\frac{d\alpha}{dt} - \left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\right)\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)\right) \quad (36)$$

which at equilibrium gives,

$$\left(\frac{\partial\sigma_s}{\partial\alpha}\right)^e = 0 \quad (37)$$

Thus we need to go for the second order term. The second derivative of σ_s is obtained from eq. (36) that reads as,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2\sigma_s}{\partial\alpha^2} = & -\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial\alpha^2}\left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\right)\right)\frac{d\alpha}{dt} - \frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial\alpha^2}\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)\right) \\ & - 2\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\right)\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)\right) \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

which in the limit of equilibrium reads as,

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2\sigma_s}{\partial\alpha^2}\right)^e = -2\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\right)\right)^e\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)\right)^e \quad (39)$$

The sign of $(\partial^2\sigma_s/\partial\alpha^2)^e$ is required to be established. Thus, this gets established in the case of a single chemical reaction $A \rightleftharpoons B$ as follows. The rate of the considered chemi-

cal reaction is given by,

$$\frac{d\xi}{dt} = k_f A - k_r B \quad (40)$$

where k_f and k_r are the forward and reverse rate constants respectively and A and B in eq. (40) stand for the respective mole numbers. In terms of perturbation eq. (40) gets expressed as,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = -(k_f + k_r)\alpha < 0 \quad (41)$$

Therefore, we obtain,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right) = -(k_f + k_r) = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)\right)^e < 0 \quad (42)$$

whereas the sign of $(\partial(\mathcal{A}/T)/\partial\alpha)^e$ is established as follows,

$$\frac{\partial(\mathcal{A}/T)}{\partial\alpha} = \frac{\partial(\mathcal{A}/T)}{\partial\xi} \frac{\partial\xi}{\partial\alpha} = \frac{1}{T}\left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial\xi^2}\right) \quad (43)$$

which, in view of $(\partial^2 G/\partial\xi^2)^2 > 0^{6,7,10,11,13,15}$, in the limit of equilibrium is obtained as positive, that is we have,

$$\left(\frac{\partial(\mathcal{A}/T)}{\partial\alpha}\right)^e = \left(\frac{\partial(\mathcal{A}/T)}{\partial\xi} \frac{\partial\xi}{\partial\alpha}\right)^e = \frac{1}{T}\left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial\xi^2}\right)^e > 0 \quad (44)$$

Thus the total time rate of L_s is obtained by using eqs. (29), 42 and (44) as,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = -2\alpha\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\right)\right)^e\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right)\right)^e \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (45)$$

Therefore, the chemical equilibrium is asymptotically stable and stable under the constantly acting small disturbances.

Perturbation of temperature of the system :

If the perturbation is that of temperature, namely :

$$\alpha = (T - T^e) \quad (46)$$

Eq. (37) still remains valid because the entropy source strength reads as that given by eq. (31) and hence one should go for the second derivative of σ_s that gives,

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2\sigma_s}{\partial\alpha^2}\right)^e = 2\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T}\right)\right)^e\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial\alpha}\left(\frac{d\xi}{dt}\right)\right)^e > 0 \quad (47)$$

The positive sign of inequality in eq. (47) gets established as follows,

$$L_s = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha^2} \right)^e \alpha^2$$

$$= 2 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T} \right) \right)^e \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{d\xi}{dt} \right) \right)^e \alpha^2 > 0 \quad (48)$$

as α^2 is positive the other terms on the right hand side of eq. (48) taken together are obtained as positive. The local time derivative of L_s in the perturbation space is identically obtained as zero and the gradient of L_s in the perturbation space is computed from eq. (48) and reads as,

$$\left(\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \alpha} \right) = 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \sigma_s}{\partial \alpha^2} \right)^e \alpha > 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (49)$$

On perturbation one may have $(T - T^e) > 0$ or $(T - T^e) < 0$ and if the chemical equilibrium gets perturbed then according to LeChatelier principle^{7,15} the net rate of reaction will get set-in in such a direction so that T starts approaching T^e , that is the magnitude of α decreases in time ($d|\alpha|/dt < 0$). Hence, the total time derivative of L_s reads as,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = 2\alpha \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{\mathcal{A}}{T} \right) \right)^e \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\frac{d\xi}{dt} \right) \right)^e \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (50)$$

as α and $d\alpha/dt$ have opposite signs. In this case too the chemical equilibrium is asymptotically stable and stable under the constantly acting small disturbances.

The case of rigid body heat conduction. A case of nonequilibrium

Let us consider the case of rigid body heat conduction and further assume that it follows the Maxwell-Cattaneo-Vernotte (MCV) equation both on the perturbed and unperturbed trajectories, namely^{23,24} :

$$\tau \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = -q - (\lambda \nabla T)^0 \quad (51)$$

$$\tau \frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} = -q^0 - (\lambda \nabla T)^0 \quad (52)$$

where τ is the relaxation time ($\sim 10^{-12}$ s)²³⁻²⁵, q is the heat flux density, T is the temperature, λ is the thermal conductivity and t is time. Recall that, Chetayev¹ has categorically clarified that – in the Lyapunov definition of stability it is assumed that there are no perturbation forces, i.e. that the perturbed motion occurs under the action of the same external forces which are taken into account in determining

the unperturbed motion. In view of this we have retained the same value of gradient of temperature in eqs. (51) and (52). Next to construct the thermodynamic perturbation space we borrow the extended Gibbs relation that given by the extended irreversible thermodynamics (EIT)²⁵. In the present case it reads as,

$$\rho \frac{ds}{dt} = T^{-1} \rho \frac{du}{dt} - \gamma_q q \cdot \frac{\partial q}{\partial t} \quad (53)$$

and the corresponding internal energy balance equation reads as,

$$\rho \frac{du}{dt} = -\text{div} q \quad (54)$$

where s is per unit mass entropy and u is the per unit mass internal energy. Further, EIT gives the following expression for the entropy source strength, σ_s , namely :

$$\sigma_s = \mu q \cdot q > 0 \quad (55)$$

where $\mu = (\lambda T^2)^{-1} > 0$ and $\gamma_q > 0$ gets equated to $\tau/\lambda T^2 > 0$. The positive sign of σ_s basically stems from the Clausius-Duhem inequality²⁶, namely :

$$\rho \frac{ds}{dt} + \text{div} J_s = \sigma_s > 0 \quad (56)$$

which is the local level version of Clausius' inequality. Notice that eq. (55) describes how this dictate of the second law of thermodynamics is followed in the present case. In eq. (56) J_s is the entropy flux density.

The extended Gibbs relation, eq. (53), indicates that the thermodynamic independent variables are u and q . Accordingly, the perturbation coordinates δu and δq get defined as,

$$\delta u = (u - u^0), \delta q = (q - q^0). \quad (57)$$

We need to keep in mind that in Lyapunov sense δu and δq are the sufficiently small perturbations but not the infinitesimal ones in the strict mathematical sense.

The equations of motion within the thermodynamic perturbation space are then obtained as,

$$\frac{d\delta q}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\tau} \delta q \quad (58)$$

$$\frac{d\delta u}{dt} = -\text{div} \delta q \quad (59)$$

In the present case L_s reads as (cf. eq. (11)),

$$L_s = (\sigma_s - \sigma_s^0) = \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \ddot{\mathbf{a}}q} \right)^0 \cdot \delta q \geq 0 \quad (60)$$

We have retained in eq. (60) only one perturbation co-ordinate as eq. (56) does not involve u explicitly and hence the only perturbation coordinate that matters is δq . Thus from eq. (55) we obtain,

$$\left(\frac{\partial \sigma_s}{\partial \ddot{\mathbf{a}}q} \right)^0 = 2\mu q^0 \geq 0 \quad (61)$$

and hence on substituting eq. (61) in eq. (60) the thermodynamic Lyapunov function reads as,

$$L_s = (\sigma_s - \sigma_s^0) \approx 2\mu q^0 \cdot \delta q \geq 0 \quad (62)$$

The sign of L_s is determined by the sign of $q^0 \cdot \delta q$ as $\mu > 0$. The local time derivative of L_s , in the perturbation space, is obtained from eq. (62) as,

$$\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial t} = 2\mu \delta q \cdot \frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} \geq 0 \quad (63)$$

and the gradient of L_s , in perturbation space, is obtained as,

$$\frac{\partial L_s}{\partial \ddot{\mathbf{a}}q} = 2\mu q^0 \geq 0 \text{ and finite} \quad (64)$$

The total time derivative of L_s is obtained from eqs. (58), (63) and (64) as,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = 2\mu \left[\frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} - \frac{q^0}{\tau} \right] \cdot \delta q \quad (65)$$

The stability inferences follow from eq. (65) as under, namely :

(i) The stability of a NSS is ascertained from eq. (65), which now reads as,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} = -\frac{2\mu}{\tau} q^0 \cdot \delta q \geq 0 \quad (66)$$

Hence, we have,

$$L_s > 0 \text{ and } \frac{dL_s}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0$$

$$L_s < 0 \text{ and } \frac{dL_s}{dt} \geq \beta > 0 \quad (67)$$

as at NSS we have,

$$\left(\frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} \right)^{\dots} = 0 \quad (68)$$

Thus the considered NSS is established as asymptotically stable and also stable under constantly acting small disturbances. This is one particular example of our earlier generalized demonstration using CTTSIP that all NSS are asymptotically stable and also stable under constantly acting small disturbances¹⁸.

(ii) The stability of a time dependent nonequilibrium state of the rigid body heat conduction follows as under.

(a) For a perturbation with $q^0 \cdot \delta q > 0$ that is $L_s > 0$ the asymptotic stability and stability under constantly acting

small disturbances emerge if either $\delta q \cdot \frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} < 0$ or

$\delta q \cdot \frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} > 0$ along with $\left| \frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} \right| < \left| \frac{\partial q^0}{\tau} \right|$. That is, in this case we have,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} \leq -\beta < 0 \quad (69)$$

(b) For a perturbation with $q^0 \cdot \delta q < 0$ that is $L_s < 0$ the asymptotic stability and stability under constantly acting

small disturbances emerge only if $\delta q \cdot \frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} < 0$ along with

$\left| \frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} \right| > \left| \frac{q^0}{\tau} \right|$. That is, in this case we have,

$$\frac{dL_s}{dt} \geq \beta > 0 \quad (70)$$

(c) An interesting case of stability whether $L_s > 0$ or $L_s < 0$ is obtained when,

$$\frac{\partial q^0}{\partial t} = \frac{q^0}{\tau} \quad (71)$$

which implies that $2q^0 = -\tau (\lambda \nabla T)^0$ in the corresponding non-stationary nonequilibrium state.

Thus outside the domain of above conditions the instability against perturbations is obtained in the time dependent process of rigid body heat conduction.

Concluding remarks

Recall that in Gibbs-Duhem stability description of

chemical equilibrium^{6,7} one relies on the impossibility of negative entropy production and hence on the negative sign of $(\partial(A/T)/\partial\xi)^e$. This makes Gibbs-Duhem stability theory geometrical in nature as therein one considers a hypothetical virtual displacement from equilibrium. Whereas in CTTSIP (as described above) we have considered a real perturbation and determined the nature of the process that follows. We recall that the stability of chemical equilibrium against the perturbation in temperature has been discussed earlier^{7,15} but with an aim to substantiate LeChatelier principle using total differential of chemical affinity and then imposing condition of chemical equilibrium. Moreover, the present author has discussed earlier¹⁶ the question of stability of the rigid body heat conduction using CTTSIP framework. However, the same conclusions are obtained in the presently described setup of CTTSIP but quite lucidly and with much better clarity. The same is the position of our present conclusions about the stability of equilibrium states including NSS vis-à-vis the earlier conclusions¹⁸. Moreover, it would be interesting to investigate above problems by a method described earlier¹⁴ that is based on the rules of Markov processes and see how far the two methods are compatible.

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